

O'QUVCHI YOSHLARNI KASBGA YO'NALTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK OMILLARI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6805324>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th June 2022

Accepted: 01st July 2022

Online: 07th July 2022

KEY WORDS

profession, psychologist, vocational training, DDS, Human-artistic image, Human-characters, Human-human, Human-technique, Human-nature.

ABSTRACT

Vocational guidance of students has always been one of the priorities of our state. The role of parents of our children and educational institutions, as well as the work of teachers and practicing psychologists working there, is of great importance for the implementation of this process. This article gives a brief overview of the current problems of vocational guidance of students, shortcomings in practice and ways to overcome them. In addition, a DDS on vocational guidance of schoolchildren was conducted, empirical analysis was made, conclusions and recommendations were given.

Introduction: During his visit to Fergana, President Mirziyoyev gave special instructions to the Ministry of Public Education. The President touched upon the issues of youth employment and vocational guidance, emphasizing the need to direct students to the profession from the 7th grade in the new school year. According to the President's instructions to the Minister of Public Education Sh. Shermatov, starting from the 7th grade in the 2020-2021 academic year, students will be directed to a profession, and it will be determined what kind of profession they will have. Until the 8th, 9th, and 10th grades, they are trained in their chosen profession. In 10th grade, they are issued work certificates. In the 11th grade, students will be able to work in companies and organizations and receive a salary at the same time. Governors and regional sector leaders are

responsible for the employment of 11th grade graduates.

Based on these views, it can be said that the employment of young people, their orientation to a conscious profession is one of the priorities of state policy. In this regard, it is important to direct school graduates to the profession, to choose the right profession based on their interests and abilities. This puts a lot of responsibility on school psychologists.

A profession is a special form of social organization of able-bodied people in a society, combined with the general type of activity and professional consciousness of its members. In his scientific work, EA Klimov puts forward the following definition: "Profession is a necessary and valuable field for society, in which a person requires physical and mental strength." appearing as Elaborating on this definition, EA Klimov defines professional activity as a

qualitatively historically evolving system and an area of self-expression. VG Makushin says that a profession is an activity through which a person participates in the life of society and serves as the main source of material means for his survival. Everyone should be interested in the profession of their choice, have a certain vision of the profession, be physically fit for a certain professional training, have the necessary qualities for professional activity. should be available.

In our study, we conducted a "Differential Diagnostic Questionnaire" proposed by the Russian scientist EA

Klimov in order to determine which areas students have a focus. A total of 223 11th graders from schools with low enrollment in higher education participated in our study. We conducted our study in two phases. In the first stage, we conducted a "Differential Diagnostic Survey". In the second stage, the results from the respondents were processed (ie, statistical analysis).

Initially, we conducted a DDS to determine which area the students were focusing on. The results from the respondents are presented in the following table (Table 1).

Table 1

No	Directions	soni	percent
1	Human-artistic image	19	8,5
2	Human characters	14	6,3
3	Man-to-man	71	31,8
4	Man-technique	28	12,6
5	Man-nature	17	7,6
6	There is hesitation	74	33,2
Total		223	100

It can be seen from this table that 31.8% of the respondents focused on the field of "Human-to-Human" and showed such qualities as communicativeness, ability to communicate with people, understanding their interests and willingness to help them. They can work in professions (salesman, hairdresser, teacher, nurse, lawyer) that deal with people, groups, communities, social processes. 12.6% of the respondents said that they are interested in the field of "Human-Technique" and have a high level of technical thinking, spatial imagery, development of coordination, accuracy of

movements and interest in technical equipment. They can work in several fields, such as engineer-technologist, engineer-electrician, builder-engineer. 8.6% of the respondents focused on the field of "Human-artistic image" and showed that they have a special ability for a particular artistic activity, imagination, impression, figurative memory, figurative thinking, aesthetic taste. They can work in many professions such as artist, decorator, director, critic, makeup artist. 7.6% of respondents focused on the field of "Human-Nature", they showed such qualities as observation, perseverance,

endurance, patience, foresight, love of all living things. Such students can work effectively in a variety of activities, such as zoomengineering, agronomy, and chemistry. 6.3% of the respondents showed a focus on the “Human-Character” field, as well as qualities such as endurance, patience, attention, reverse memory, accuracy of perception, ability to work with numbers, images, tables and diagrams.

Such students can work effectively in a number of fields, such as computer operator, telegraph operator, graphic designer, accountant. However, the majority of respondents in our survey showed that they were hesitant to choose a suitable profession and lacked understanding of professions and were hesitant to choose an independent profession.

The results from the respondents are as follows (Diagram 1).

Figure 1

The results obtained from the DDS respondents are presented in the following

table to determine gender differences (Table 2).

Table 2

№	Directions	Boys		Girls		percentage difference
		soni	percent	soni	percent	
1	Human-artistic image	7	5,6	12	12,2	6,6
2	Human characters	10	8	4	4,1	-3,9
3	Man-to-man	30	24	41	41,9	17,9
4	Man-technique	23	18,4	5	5,1	-13,3
5	Man-nature	12	9,6	5	5,1	-4,5
6	There is hesitation	43	34,4	31	31,6	-2,8

total	125	100	98	100
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* Note: - indicates the dominance of boys.

From this table it can be seen that in the field of "Human-artistic image" 6.6% of girls, in the field of "Human-characters" 3.9% of boys, "Man-man" In the field of "Human-Technology" - 17.9%, girls, in the field of "Human-Technology" - 13.3%, and in the field of "Human-Nature" - 4.5%. 'gil

children made up the majority. With 2.8 percent, boys are more hesitant to choose a career than girls.

A comparative view of the results obtained from the respondents with the indicators of boys and girls has the following diagram form (Diagram 2).

The results of the study show that most young people today are focused on the field of "man-to-man" and show such qualities as openness to communication, ability to communicate with people, understanding their interests and willingness to help them. we can see. Also, the fact that the majority of respondents in our study did

not make a decision in choosing a profession, the lack of understanding of the profession creates hesitation in their choice of profession. The school practitioner psychologist should conduct individual interviews with students with hesitation and provide insights into their careers.

References:

1. Usmonova M. D., Parpiyev O. A. PROBLEM OF PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH IN EDUCATION // Psixologicheskoye zdorovye naseleniya kak vajnyy faktor obespecheniya prosvetaniya obshcheystva. - 2020. - P. 287-289.
2. Sardor Gayrat Ugli Umirzokov, and Aziza Mirzabekovna Sayubova. "PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS" Academic research in educational sciences, vol. 2, no. Special Issue 1, 2021, pp. 432-437.

3. Abdulazizova X. M., Usmonova M. D. PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH IN CHOICE OF PROFESSION // Psixologicheskoye zdorovye naseleniya kak vajnyy faktor obespecheniya prosvetaniya obshcheystva. - 2020. - P. 234-236.
4. Qodirov B.R., Azimova A.F. Methods of determining the abilities of students. –Т.: 2017. В-7
5. Usmonov, S. A. (2020). OPPORTUNITIES WITH WORKING ABILITY CHILDREN IN EDUCATION. In Психологическое здоровье населения как важный фактор обеспечения процветания общества (pp. 298-300).
6. Usmonov, S. A. (2020). PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS WITH WORKING ABILITY CHILDREN. In Психологическое здоровье населения как важный фактор обеспечения процветания общества (pp. 177-179).
7. Usmonov, S. A., & Xoldaraliyeva, A. A. Q. (2021). TALABA YOSHLARNI TOLERANTLIK RUHIDA TARBIYALASHNING PSIXOLOGIK TAMOILLARI. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(5), 73-77.
8. Усмонов, Ш. А., Закирова, М. С., & Нуриддинов, Р. С. Ў. (2021). ИЛК ЎСПИРИНЛИК ДАВРИДА АҚЛИЙ ҚОБИЛИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЭМПИРИК ТАҲЛИЛИ. Современное образование (Узбекистан), (9 (106)), 12-16.
9. Axmadjonovich, U. S. (2022). EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS ON MASTERY INDICATORS IN STUDENTS.
10. Usmanov, S., & Absalomov, E. U. (2020). IMPROVEMENT OF TOLERANT CULTURE IN THE FAMILY. Theoretical & Applied Science, (1), 674-676.